

PHENOMENON OF METAPHORIZATION IN LITERATURE

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Abstract. *The analysis has been made from different perspectives such as: historical, lexical and semantic. It is very important to understand the historical formation of the process as well as its correlation with lexical and semantic aspects of the linguistic. Specific metaphor properties are the reason why a very important role in a language is dedicated to the metaphor. Language embodiment of new concepts and a creation of new linguistic manners is a direct consequence of the metaphORIZATION process. Certain linguistic forms are a place of a realization of cognitive reality images. These images are based on a metaphorical transference.*

Keywords: *metaphor; metaphORIZATION, metaphorical realization, concept, English literature.*

ФЕНОМЕН МЕТАФОРИЗАЦИИ В ЛИТЕРАТУРЕ

Аннотация. *Проведен анализ с разных точек зрения, таких как: исторический, лексический и семантический. Очень важно понять историческое формирование процесса, а также его взаимосвязь с лексическими и семантическими аспектами языка. Специфические свойства метафоры являются причиной того, что метафоре отводится очень важная роль в языке. Языковое воплощение новых понятий и создание новых языковых манер является прямым следствием процесса метафоризации. Определенные языковые формы являются местом реализации когнитивных образов действительности. Эти образы основаны на метафорическом переносе.*

Ключевые слова: *метафора; метафоризация, метафорическая реализация, концепт, английская литература.*

The metaphORIZATION depends on the period of the English history. Modern metaphorical realization of the time concept has changed many times but the basic metaphorical associations remained nondeformed. There are prepositions which classified by the agentic / non-agentic feature. It's been made in order to understand time properties and in order to find correlation between the TIME concept and other aspects of the textual reality. The analysis of the chosen material has led to the distinction of five predicate groups such as: activity, location, status, quality and process. The classification of the prepositions was made in the research. They were distinguished according to the predicates.

It's a well-known fact that the metaphorization process is a very peculiar phenomenon which usually can be found in literature texts. A great number of authors use metaphorization to emphasize some concepts in their poems, novels, fairy tales, short stories etc. One of the most interesting concepts that can be distinguished in the English literature is the TIME concept. Time has been the main subject of interest of many writers. And each writer has tried to invent their own personal and unique metaphors in order to represent the Problems of the metaphorical functioning and the metaphorization process are the subject of many scientific works. "Metaphorization is the creation of a verbal image by means of a metaphor. The lexical metaphorization as a stylistic matter deeply absorbs all the functional styles of modern literary speech. The metaphorization to a great extent stylistically enriches all the speech in various spheres of its functioning"¹. "Metaphorization is an extension of the semantic volume of lexemes due to the appearance of their figurative meanings and the enhancement of its expressive properties"².

New problems and questions about studying of the metaphorization process and the metaphor phenomenon appear in linguistic science every day. According to this fact it is possible to say that the very essence of hemetaphor isn't analyzed enough nowadays. "Any speech is a labyrinth of many trails. You go from one side and you know where you are; you come to the same place from the other side and you don't know where you are and where to go next". It is statement is a proof of the actual need in searching ways of metaphorical nature explanation, its functional variety, metaphorical mechanisms and other aspects that is related to it.

A metaphor is considered to be a linguistic phenomenon which happens to be in a certain relation with the existence manner in a text world. "A metaphor is not so much a reduced comparison, but an implicit opposition. The cognitive metaphor is directed primarily at the achievement of epistemological goals. From the means of creating an image a metaphor becomes a manner of contents forming. A lack of those contents in language result this kind of forming"³ "A metaphor is represented in a substitutional paradigm as a word (lexeme, concept, definition) replacement with other word (lexeme, concept, definition)"⁴. The speech and cognition are not the frames that limit the sphere of a metaphor using. "A metaphor is a semantic process. According to the process the form of a linguistic unit or design of a language category is transferred from one object of designation to another. A metaphor might be named as a manner of knowledge realization

¹ Shevchenko, 2010, pp. 354.

² Karpilovs'ka, 2010, pp. 29.

³ Arutyunova, 1990, pp. 23.

⁴ Yeshchenko, 2001, pp. 85.

in a verbal form and as an expression of everyday conceptual implementation. A metaphor is one of the main tropes. It's a word or word-combination which reveals the essence and the characteristics of a certain phenomenon through a transfer of similar features and properties of another phenomenon.

The approaches to metaphor in literature we have discussed so far do not all belong to the same tradition, but they have a number of important similarities. Even though all recognize that metaphor is not an exclusively literary phenomenon, they emphasize the discontinuity between metaphor in literature and metaphor elsewhere by focusing on highly creative, original and often complex literary examples. Their aim is to investigate the uses of metaphor in particular texts, genres, or authors, and to explain how particular linguistic choices in particular contexts lead to particular effects. They therefore emphasize the uniqueness of each particular use of metaphor in literature, and offer analyses and interpretations that can often be appreciated for their depth and richness regardless of whether one shares the particular scholar's theoretical assumptions. These studies also provide extensive accounts of the variety of metaphorical structures that can be found in literature, and of their potential effects. When they consider the relationship between literary and non-literary metaphors, the studies discussed in this section tend to attribute primacy to metaphor in literature, and hence to see metaphors outside literature as largely derivative, and therefore less worthy of investigation. Leech puts it thus: In the dictum 'Language is fossil poetry', Emerson draws our attention to the fact that the expressive power of everyday language largely resides in countless 'dead' metaphors, which have become institutionalized in the multiple meanings of the dictionary.

On the face of it, it is hard to reconcile the approaches to metaphor in literature we have discussed in this section with those we discussed in the previous section. Indeed, the mutual attacks (and partial misrepresentations) of the main proponents of the different approaches do little to promote dialogue and convergence.

However, we hope to have shown that, in spite of sometimes profound theoretical differences, each approach can contribute in significant ways to our understanding and appreciation of the workings of metaphor in literature. While it is important to recognize the different structures and potential effects of metaphor in literature and the unique characteristics of each individual example, it is also crucial to appreciate the strength of the connections between creative and conventional uses of metaphor.

Specific metaphor properties are the reason why a very important role in a language is dedicated to the metaphor. Language embodiment of new concepts and a creation of new linguistic

manners is a direct consequence of the metaphorization process. Certain linguistic forms are a place of a realization of cognitive reality images. these images are based on a metaphorical transference.

REFERENCES

1. Burroughs S. William (2004) Naked Lunch. / Grove/Atlantic, p. 289.
2. Cocker, E. Cocker's Arithmetick. Printed for Mess. Bettesworth and Hitch, at the Redlyon in Pater-noster row; R. Ware, at the Sun and Bible in Amen-corner; and J. Hodges, at the Looking-glass on London-bridge, 1736. 183 p.
3. Corpus of Middle English Prose and Verse. University of Michigan. URL: <http://quod.lib.umich.edu/c/cme/> (access date 20.04.2016)
4. Dickens Charles (2006) Bleak House. London: Penguin Books, p. 1017.
5. Jalilovna, K. S. (2022). Common Similarities and Differences of Uzbek and English Fairy Tales. European Journal of Innovation in Nonformal Education, 2(1), 366-369.
6. Khalilova, S. (2022). PHILOSOPHICAL ASPECTS OF GLOBALIZATION. Gospodarka i Innowacje., 28, 6-11.
7. Jalilovna, K. S. (2022). COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF UZBEK AND ENGLISH FAIRY TALES. IJTIMOIIY FANLARDA INNOVASIYA ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI, 80-83.
8. Jalilovna, K. S. (2022, February). A CASE STUDY ON VOCABULARY LEARNING THROUGH READING FAIRY TALES. In E-Conference Globe (pp. 5-6).
9. Khalilova, S. (2023). TIME AND SPACE IN THE PHILOSOPHY OF IBN SINA: OBJECTIVITY AND CONNECTION WITH MATTER. American Journal of Research in Humanities and Social Sciences, 16, 93-98.
10. Khalilova, S. (2023). THE VALUE OF THE HERITAGE OF ABU ALI IBN SINA IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF YOUTH EDUCATION. American Journal of Research in Humanities and Social Sciences, 14, 146-151.